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***Cyclopsocus hyalinus* THORNTON & SMITHERS, 1984
– a new record of barkfly (Psocodea: Psocomorpha:
Calopsocidae) for continental Asia**

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Abstract: The psocid species *Cyclopsocus hyalinus* THORNTON & SMITHERS, 1984 from the family Calopsocidae is recorded for the fauna of Thailand for the first time. In total, 38 psocid species are known from Thailand. The species was collected in January 2014 in Sakaerat Environmental Research Station in the evergreen forest by light trap. This species is known only from its type locality in New Guinea. The present find is new for continental Asia.

Key words: Psocoptera, new record, fauna, Thailand.

INTRODUCTION

So far, about 5500 species of barkflies (Psocoptera) have been described in the world, and their greatest differentiation occurs in tropical and subtropical zones (LIENHARD 2016). The free-living members of the order Psocodea ('Psocoptera') are poorly known in Thailand. To date, 38 species have been recorded (LIENHARD 2016, GEORGIEV 2023). In this short note we report of one species not previously discovered in this area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Cyclopsocus hyalinus THORNTON & SMITHERS, 1984 was identified by analyzing the materials from studies of the Psocoptera fauna of Thailand carried out in 2014. This species was collected in the evergreen forest by light trapping. The specimen was stored in 96% ethanol. The species identification is based on the original description and the keys by THORNTON & SMITHERS (1984).

RESULTS

Cyclopsocus hyalinus THORNTON & SMITHERS, 1984 (Fig. 1)

Material examined: Thailand, Sakaerat Environmental Research Station (14°30'N/101°55'E), 25 I 2014, 1♂, evergreen forest, light trap, J. Gorczyca leg., D. Georgiev det. The examined specimen was deposited in the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom (USMB).

Distribution. Known only from its type locality in New Guinea (THORNTON & SMITHERS 1984). New record for continental Asia.

Notes. The examined male specimen fits well with the description of THORNTON & SMITHERS (1984). The animal is hyaline-yellowish-white with black compound eyes. The forewing and its veins are hyaline, Rs is 3 branched. The phallosome has 3 pairs of sclerites.

Fig. 1. *Cyclopsocus hyalinus*, male specimen from Thailand: A – habitus, lateral; B – ninth tergite, dorsal; C – phallosome; (B and C not to scale). Photos by D. Georgiev.

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